

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B427

Date: 30 Jan 2009

Take Off: 09:35:22

Landing: 10:47:39 10:42:39 in database?

Flight Time: 1h12m17

Campaign: APPRAISE - Flight aborted due to aircraft technical problems (nosewheel)

Operating Area:

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Latti Lathouwers	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Al Foster	Directflight	
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Zhiqiang Cui	Leeds University	
6	Flight Manager / WAS	Mo Smith	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics / Core Chem	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
8	Wet Neph / PSAP / Filters	Simon Osborne	Met Office	
9	AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
10	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester University	
11	CVI	Jeff Norwood Brown	Met Office	
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

The following log sheets are not available for this flight :

Log	Reason
Track plot	No plot available
Xchat	No log available as flight aborted
Cloud Physics In Flight	No log available as flight aborted
Cloud Physics Processing	No log available as flight aborted
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log available as flight aborted
Filters	No log available as flight aborted
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
Wet Neph	No log available as flight aborted
CVI	No log available as flight aborted
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	30 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

no data on BADC 30 Dec 2009

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b427

Date: 30 January 2009

Project: APPRAISE - Flight aborted due to aircraft technical problems (nosewheel)

Location: Cranfield

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
082759		Start-Up	0.27 kft	211	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
091417		Event	0.27 kft	129	2 x GPU outage
092649		ASP	0.27 kft	097	Open
093522		T/O	1.6 kft	042	Cranfield
100020		Event	0.00 kft	133	Holding pattern
104739		Land	0.28 kft	261	Cranfield
104931		ASP	0.27 kft	255	Close
105114		Shutdown	0.27 kft	307	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

Sortie Brief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies

Date: 30 Jan 2009

B427 t/o (Cranfield) 09:30z

M.Sci: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in clouds (probably mid-high level on this occasion) associated with fronts lying N-S over the middle of the country - in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Sortie Location: Over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. Area Alpha.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs at a series of altitudes below cloud base (if possible), within and above the cloud, along the azimuth that is being scanned by the radar. Information on the run orientation and altitude to be flown will be provided by scientists at Chilbolton using VHF radio (call-sign "Radsearch"). Where the radar identifies a small-scale feature of interest, the aircraft may abort a long leg in order to turn to re-penetrate it. Where either the aircraft or radar identifies a particular horizontal layer of interest, the aircraft may fly a sawtooth pattern so as to provide a sequence of profiles through it. It is desired that the aircraft flight legs start/finish in the Chilbolton overhead. This benefits the validation of vertically-pointing radar/lidar retrievals of supercooled cloud layers. This requires turns to be done within controlled airspace and so may limit the number of occasions that this is possible.

Sortie Detail :

- a) T+0 Take off & climb to FL100 to transit to operating area at Chilbolton.
- b) T+35 When at suitable location descend from transit altitude to 1000ft agl, or to lowest altitude allowed by operating restrictions. Fly 10min **clear air** leg in vicinity of Chilbolton.
- c) Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min along the azimuth and through the cloud system up to FL330 or to above cloud top, whichever is lower.
- d) Fly a series of 40-60km level flight legs along the azimuth scanned by the radar at altitudes defined by the radar or as determined from previous profile. Ideally, just above cloud base, throughout the cloud, just below and just above cloud top. Duration of each leg ~10 minutes. Legs should extend over Chilbolton. During incloud legs AMS should sample off CVI inlet unless tip iced up (but sample off Rosemount inlet out of cloud). Filters to be exposed on out of cloud legs only.
- e) Where the radar identifies a feature of interest or one that is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, the leg may be interrupted to fly one or more butterfly patterns. Each butterfly consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern.
- f) Where a defined layer of interest (such as a shallow layer of supercooled liquid water) is identified by the aircraft or radar, the long leg may be flown as a sawtooth leg with ascents/descents at 1000ft/min, extending 1000ft above and below the layer level (M.Sci may request level segments of 1 minute).
- g) Repeat items d) to e) as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit.
- h) End with below-cloud clear air aerosol leg (10 min) if possible, before recovering to destination airfield.

PROJECT BRIEF: APPRAISE-Clouds – mixed-phase cloud studies

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems, altocumulus clouds, wave clouds and cumulus clouds within the temperature regime in which ice particles will likely co-exist with liquid (typically 0 to -30C).

The flight plans are designed to characterise the aerosol above and below the cloud and infer aerosol fluxes into the cloud layer by combination with the vertical wind measurements and the microphysical characteristics within the cloud layer.

Constant altitude flight legs of approximately 50 km (10 minutes flying) will be made:

- In the boundary layer to measure the aerosol size distributions (from 10 nm to 100 um), CCN, aerosol composition from 30 nm to 1 um using the ToF AMS; larger particles and non-volatile material such as refractory material will be measured using EDAX analysis of filter samples.
- Near cloud base within cloud to measure the cloud droplets that have been activated from CCN, interstitial particles and larger particles that have fallen from cloud top. In addition the onset of ice will be observed using the CPI, CAPS and 2-D probes in cloud.
- Middle of the cloud passes will be made at temperatures where key processes will be expected to be initiated (-6C to -9C) for the Hallett-Mossop process or around -15C where fragmentation of dendritic crystals may be important.
- Near cloud top and within the cloud to measure entrainment and aerosols within entrained eddies and ice particles within the cloud; in colder clouds ice initiation will occur in this region.
- Above the cloud to measure the properties of aerosol particles that can potentially be entrained into the clouds.

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the CAMRa radar and lidar facilities at Chilbolton, Hants.

Weather conditions: Stratiform, or altocumulus clouds lying over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer, CR2
- GPS, GIN, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud/Aerosol Physics/Chemistry

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- 2DS, CAPS and FSSP – as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.
- AMS, SMPS/WCPC (- to sample off both Rosemount and CVI inlets)
- Filters

CVI inlet sampling: residuals (and $Ly\alpha$) incloud; aerosols out of cloud (PCASP, CPC)

Mission Scientist Debrief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies:
Flight Number: B427, 30th Jan 2009 (Take-off 9:35z, landing 10:47z)
Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal clouds in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Weather conditions & operating area: A blocking high pressure region centred over Scandinavia was steering a low pressure area to the west of the British Isles along a trajectory northwards along the 15°W longitude line. At midnight the low was due west of Ireland and by midday had progressed northwards to be west of northern Scotland. Associated with the low pressure system were two fronts. The most easterly of these was oriented N-S and positioned across the tip of Cornwall at midnight. At this stage it was classified as an occlusion. Further west was a cold front which stretched the whole length of the British Isles and south to the west of Iberia, and was positioned through the middle of Ireland at midnight. The occlusion was forecasted to move steadily eastwards during the morning before being brought to a halt sometime during the middle of the day, N-S across central England. At this point it was expected to be pushed back westwards (particularly in the south) by the influence of the high pressure over Europe. However significant cloudcover was forecasted to be present over the western half of southern England (approximately from Chilbolton and to the west – see Met Office mesoscale model output below), particularly at mid levels, throughout the afternoon. Based on this forecast a 09:00z takeoff time was set so as to catch the maximum extent of cloud cover at Chilbolton.

Summary of the flight: The aircraft lost power from the GPU prior to boarding. This significantly affected the AMS which partially lost its vacuum. This meant AMS measurements would probably not be useful during the flight. However, all cloud microphysical instrumentation seemed to be OK so a decision was made to carry out the flight. When an attempt was made to start engines the GPU again failed. This time CPI was affected but recovered its comms after a short hold on the taxiway, so again the decision was made to proceed with the flight. Takeoff was at 09:35z. Unfortunately, an aircraft problem occurred after take-off. The nose gear did not give an all clear indication of having locked up. After cycling through procedures, the undercarriage locked in the down position. The aircraft was then required to land so flew with full flaps and airbrakes

(and undercarriage down) to burn off fuel quickly to enable a landing to be made. The aircraft landing at 10:47z. No useful science was therefore carried out on this flight.

Notes on instrumentation:

AMS – the partial loss of vacuum seemed to have affected the filament. After power was restored it was glowing more brightly than operators could ever remember seeing. It was considered that this may have been a signal of imminent failure. To prevent a catastrophic failure which might actually scatter debris throughout the detector region and cause contamination, and since the instrument had already lost significant vacuum, the decision was taken that the instrument rack should be removed to replace the faulty filament and to allow several days of pumping on the ground to remove the background.

(For a full list of other instrumentation functionality see flight log)

Mission Scientist's Log [APPRMSE-CLOUDS] B6

Flight No B. 427 Date 30/01/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 1 of 1

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
9.00.					lost GPU - Arms power down to 35%
					as we banded aircraft - filament on fuel blower ??
9.10					Going for engine start - power failure again
9.16.53	KNB	~9.19.	40		Engine start 4-1 - engine start OK power change over OK
					Delay - OP2 - lost d arms since had 290V out.
9.27.00					Taxi QNH 1016 1
9.30.00					Holding Short RW 03.
9.32.00	KNB				Taxi - hold 9.34.00 KNB
9.35.31					Rolling
9.36.02					710 to N - broken high dead at - A/C problem - Red on nose gear - some - ground "115" - scud. below ^{from} 1500ft. - Cheeks → gear - 3 green - Now have to burn off fuel for Zhensk!
10.47.00					130 / 110 Hz
10.48.22					Landed

Flight:

B427

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B427

Date: 30/01/09

Issues

GPU dropped out x 2 on pre-flight. Once when APU selected, then again during engine start.

Instruments

1. AMS – dropped out on pre-flight, not working properly for rest of flight
2. CPI – problem with switch on rack (damaged?) also difficulty in re-establishing comms post gpu dropouts.
3. HORACE – lots of dropouts. Improved briefly after cycling DLU CBs. DLU packets not being received continuously. Rebooted HORACE, okay for about 10 minutes then more dropouts. Tried stopping H_OPTIC. Possible network problem
4. Core Cloud Physics – problems pre taxi.
- 5.

Horace	
Dropsondes	Nil
CVI -	
Nevzorov	
Buck -	
FWVS	Not fitted
Turbulence	
2ds	
CAPS	
CDP	
Total Water	

Aircraft

1. Problem with nosewheel on take-off, would not retract. Same problem as in India. Stay in holding

SatcomC	ops normal
MPDS	
ISDN Emails	Not used
Satcom-H Calls	Nil

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 30/1/09

Flight No: B 427

Pre-Flighter: PDR

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☐	Hangar	Collect spanners	Core Chem - 9/16" & 11/16"
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☐	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	☐	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☐	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	NOT FITTED
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
24	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	NOT RUN
25	☐	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	NOT OPERATOR
26	☐	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	WEPH OPERATOR
27	☐	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	NOT FITTED
28	☒	3876 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
29	☒	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	COULD NOT REMOVE LID BUT 3 FULL SO LEFT.
30	☒	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
31	☒	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
32	☒	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
33	☒	3786 CPC	Drained	
34	☒	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
<u>External Checks</u>				
35	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
36	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
37	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
38	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
39	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
40	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
41	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
42	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
43	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
44	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
45	☒	All other covers	Removed	
46	☐	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol **
47	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
48	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
49	☐			
50	☐			
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
51	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
52	☐	ICEX applied		
53	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more